

EXPERIMENT-TESTING METHODOLOGY OF ON RAPID TEACHING OF ENGLISH TO STUDENTS IN THE CONDITONS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

Davronova Fotima Pirnazarovna

Samarkand state university veterinary medicine of livestock and biotechnologies

ANNOTATION

This article illustrates the usage of digital technologies in teaching the English language and effective results of focusing on educational activities. The usage of "Resume" technology and "Problem" technology in the rapid teaching of English to students in the context of digital technologies, based on examples. This is explained on the basis of examples of how it can be done by using methods that create multiple learning opportunities. Recommended some models of digital technologies a special emphasis was placed on rapid teaching of English to students based on giving priority to such digital technologies.

Key words: "Resume" technology, "Problem" technology, digital technology, educational program, rapid teaching.

The need to improve the system of teaching 1st-year students to use digital technologies in the educational process was proven during the research. In the process of teaching English, the wide use of information and communication technologies, authorship, interactive methods, modern pedagogical technologies, as well as the organization of the educational process with various interactive tools, including interactive whiteboards, interactive audiovisual tools, electronic textbooks and other advanced principles Enrichment and improvement of the pedagogical content of the subject became important.

"Resume" technology

Description of technology. This technology is aimed at studying complex, multidisciplinary, problem-oriented topics as much as possible, and directs students to rapid mastery of the educational material in English. The essence of the technology is that it provides information on different branches of the subject in one way. At the moment, each of them will be discussed from separate points. For example, pros and cons, advantages and disadvantages, benefits and harms are defined.

The purpose of the technology is to enable students to speak English fluently, to think independently and critically, to work as a team, to research, to find a solution to an educational problem based on the topic using the method of summarizing and

comparing facts, and to make the necessary conclusion or decision, to influence the team with their opinion, to approve it. , as well as teaching to apply the knowledge gained from the topics covered in solving the given problem, giving a general understanding of the topic.

Application of technology: it can be used in practical training in individual (or small groups) order, rapid teaching of English to students, and homework assignments.

Tools used in the training:

-The teacher introduced the students to the purpose and procedure of the exercise and distributed to each small group a sheet with a note on the upper part of the paper, i.e., the main problem, learning problems separated from it and ways to solve them, and a written summary;

The members of each group decide to define the advantages and disadvantages of the problems presented to them and explain their thoughts through the slide. Finding a solution to this problem on the basis of written opinions, he draws a general conclusion as the most acceptable option.

Students presented the educational material in English in small groups. The group's written comments were played out, but the conclusion was not presented. The teacher asks other small groups for the conclusion of the presenting group, they determine their opinion, after the opinion of the groups, the presenting group introduces its conclusion. The teacher commented on the ideas or conclusions given by the groups, evaluated them, and then ended the activity

"Problem" technology

The purpose of the technology: to teach students to quickly learn English and find solutions to problematic issues or situations arising from the topic of the subject, to form skills in determining the essence of the problem, to introduce some methods of solving the problem, and to correctly identify the causes of the problem and behavior in solving the problem to teach

Training procedure:

After dividing the students into groups and placing them in their appropriate places, the teacher explains the procedures and requirements for the exercise, that is, he says that the exercise will be phased and that each phase requires maximum attention from the students, that during the exercise they will work individually, in groups and as a team. Such a mood helps students to be ready to complete the assigned tasks and creates interest in doing them. After explaining the training procedures and requirements, the training begins:

-By carefully watching the film prepared by the students for the lesson, try to identify the problem covered in it, keep it in memory or mark it in their notebooks (if it is not possible to show a film, then the teacher will present a poster, picture, poster

or a text describing a problem on the topic of the educational subject, can use the educational material in the book);

-Each group writes down the problems identified by the members from this board (from a picture, text, life story) with a felt-tip pen on a pad or A-3 paper; After the specified time is over, the prepared work will be read out by the representative of the group;

-The teacher is selected by the groups and distributed to the groups, changing the papers on which the problems are written;

-From the problems written by the groups on the distributed papers, each group member chooses one of the problems he is interested in;

-Each member of the group writes down the chosen problem on the following diagram distributed by the teacher and analyzes it independently;

After the completion of the individual activity, each student (or pupil) reads out the analytical work he has done to everyone;

-A collective opinion on problems and their solution is shared;

After the defense, the teacher ends the lesson. Thank the small groups for their interesting work.

As a result of training with such technology, students will learn that in order to quickly learn English, before solving a problem, it is necessary to determine its cause, and then to choose the methods and methods that are necessary for them, and to clearly define their actions.

One of the most important requirements to ensure the rapid teaching of English to students is to arouse interest and activity in students. This can be achieved primarily by correctly and skillfully presenting the new material.

After the information is discussed, it is checked what other conditions are fulfilled by each specific example: As a result, in a small presentation, students will have the opportunity to write an essay in different ways. In the research text, we give examples of some essays made by students in experimental classes:

Essay on My family

Someone said, "The most important thing in the world is family and love." I think that a lot of people agree with this statement.

My family consists of four people: my lovely father, mother, elder brother and me. My father's name is Nasriddin. He had been working as a deputy manager in the mining company, before he was pensioned off. Now he is 48 and takes care of my mother and our household. By the way, he had started cooking really great dishes after he retired, it's his favorite hobby.

My mother's name is Oysha. She is an IT manager in the treasure house. She has been working with computers for as long as I remember. I think she enjoys tinkering with them and making some changes in the software. She is 42, but still looks as if she's 26. Amazing!

My parents are kind but rather strict in educating their children and grandchildren. They always give me and my brother some good advice on how to live and share their life experience with us. My elder brother works as a lawyer. His name is Doniyor. Now he lives with his own family in another country and I terribly miss our get-together time. He is quite handsome man with dark brown hair which has just started to go gray. Thank goodness, my sister-in-law is not a jealous woman. He is sincere and reliable. I can rely on him in any difficult situation. Also he is a 2-year-old girl proud father. Her name is Gulasal, and she behaves like a real queen. She always demands attention of her parents and likes to boss around a little bit. I can say that we're a very amiable family. My parents understand us at first glance, and we help each other without further ado.

Evaluation data obtained on the basis of requests for rapid teaching of English in the context of digital technologies testify to the effectiveness of the implementation of the technologies developed by us in these groups. In the context of digital technologies, the models of rapid teaching of English to students are relatively complete and effective. They embody the following structural blocks: substantive; organizational and pedagogical; criterion; diagnostic-evaluator; stepwise; operational-active; procedural-technological; consequential.

The disadvantage of individual works is that the structure of the model does not include evaluation criteria and indicators, as well as methods, tools and technologies for the development of creative, creative, professional-creative competence. In the model recommended by us, a special emphasis was placed on rapid teaching of English to students based on giving priority to such digital technologies.

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